

ON THE LINEAR VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF
REINFORCED MATERIALS

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A continuum theory is presented for the description of the isothermal linear viscoelastic stress-strain behavior of fiber reinforced anisotropic materials under arbitrary loading histories. Under the assumption, that the energy density is macroscopically reversible at inversion of time, general symmetry relations are derived for the viscoelastic after-effect tensors, describing the material properties. Explicit representations for these tensors are presented for the transversely isotropic and the orthotropic compound materials with an isotropic matrix. The given theory is generally valid in the domain of reversible stress-strain behavior independent of the choice of the materials which form the matrix and the reinforcement, i.e. it is appropriate for all compound materials.

The theoretical predictions are checked by experiments on heavily creeping glassfiber reinforced duroplastic plastics. These materials possess below certain limits of damage a linear viscoelastic and reversible stress-strain behavior such that the assumptions of the theory are satisfied. Especially, the superposition principle as well as the symmetry relations of the after-effect tensors are confirmed by experiments. In summary the following can be stated: If the independent components of the after-effect tensors (material coefficients) are established as functions of time in simple experiments under static loads, time dependent deformations for arbitrarily given loading histories (e.g. step-like, sinusoidal vibrating etc.) can be calculated by means of the theory.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced viscoelastic materials play an important role in modern plastics technology. Since the safety of a load carrying construction is often guaranteed only, if certain deformation limits are not exceeded, it is important to have accurate knowledge about the present deformation of such a material under arbitrary loading histories. The reinforced duroplastic and the amorphous thermoplastic materials possess pronounced domains of linear stress-strain behavior which in practical applications are seldom exceeded. Thus a general continuum theory of the linear viscoelastic behavior of reinforced plastics is presented. The theory is restricted to isothermal processes, and corrosion and aging effects are neglected. Although the theory is designed and experimentally checked for fiber reinforced plastics, it holds generally for other reinforced anisotropic materials in the linear viscoelastic domain of reversible stress-strain behavior.

A. Theory

1. Linear-Viscoelastic Anisotropic Materials

The general linear stress-strain relation for an anisotropic viscoelastic material is given by

$$\epsilon_{ij}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t I_{ijkl}(t-t') d\sigma_{kl}(t'). \quad (1.1)$$

$\epsilon_{ij} = \epsilon_{ji}$ denotes the deformation tensor and $\sigma_{kl} = \sigma_{lk}$ is the stress tensor. The fourth order tensor I_{ijkl} describes the viscoelastic after-effect. The tensor indices refer to an orthogonal Cartesian coordinate system. The summation convention holds, as to which summation over twice repeated indices has to be carried out from 1 to 3.

Eq. (1.1) holds only for isothermal processes and since it is time translational invariant, corrosion and aging effects are not included.

At time $t = -\infty$ the material may be in a thermostatic equilibrium under constant hydrostatic pressure and constant temperature. The corresponding deformation in this reference state may be zero. The after-effect tensor I_{ijkl} depends besides on the time parametrically on the temperature and the mass densities of the constituents of the compound material in the reference state.

Eq. (1.1) is valid for every stress history which starts at $t = -\infty$ from a hydrostatic pressure $\sigma_{ij}(-\infty) = -P\delta_{ij}$. In particular, the after-effect tensor is independent of the stress history. This is important since arbitrary stress histories will be used to determine the general properties of the after-effect tensor. Eq. (1.1) is a well known constitutive relation for the stress-strain behavior of linear viscoelastic materials. It is confirmed also by model calculations, e.g. (1), (2), (3).

From its mathematical structure eq. (1.1) is a STIELTJES integral (4) which allows to consider besides continuous stress histories also those with finite jumps.

An important observation may be added: For all continuous after-effect tensors $I_{ijkl}(t)$ and all closed stress histories $\sigma_{kl}(t) = -P\delta_{kl}$ in $t \leq t_1$ and in $t \geq t_2$ with finite $t_1 < t_2$, it is easily shown by the mean value theorem in integral calculus, that eq. (1.1) leads to a vanishing residual deformation

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \epsilon_{ij}(t) = 0. \quad (1.2)$$

Such a deformation behavior is called reversible. Hence eq. (1.1) describes the linear viscoelastic, isothermal and reversible stress-strain behavior of anisotropic materials. It will be shown later, that the reinforced plastics under consideration satisfy these properties below certain deformation limits.

Next the symmetry relations of the after-effect tensor will be derived. Since ϵ_{ij} and σ_{kl} are symmetric tensors, eq. (1.1) yields

$$I_{ijkl}(t) = I_{jikl}(t) = I_{ijlk}(t) = I_{jilk}(t), \quad t \geq 0. \quad (1.3)$$

Further symmetry relations can be proven under the assumption that an energy density W exists which is invariant against time reversal. The time derivative of W is for isothermal processes given by $\dot{W} = \sigma_{ij} \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$. Integration yields with $\epsilon_{ij}(-\infty) = 0$

$$W(t) - W(-\infty) = \sigma_{ij}(t) \epsilon_{ij}(t) - \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \epsilon_{ij}(t') \dot{\sigma}_{ij}(t'). \quad (1.4)$$

For every continuous and closed stress history the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$ exists and for all materials with reversible stress-strain behavior we obtain on account of eq. (1.2) and (1.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta W\{\sigma_{kl}(\cdot)\} &\equiv W(\infty) - W(-\infty) = \\ &= - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt \dot{\sigma}_{ij}(t) \int_{-\infty}^t dt' I_{ijkl}(t-t') \dot{\sigma}_{kl}(t'), \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

where the energy difference ΔW is a functional of the stress history. We consider now the time reversed history

$$\bar{\sigma}_{kl}(t) = \sigma_{kl}(-t). \quad (1.6)$$

The energy functional $\Delta W\{\bar{\sigma}_{kl}(\cdot)\}$ for the time reversed process transforms after insertion of eq. (1.6), interchange of integrations, after the substitutions $t \rightarrow -t$, $t' \rightarrow -t'$ and renaming of the summation indices after some calculations into

$$\Delta W\{\bar{\sigma}_{kl}(\cdot)\} = - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt \dot{\sigma}_{ij}(t) \int_{-\infty}^t dt' I_{klij}(t-t') \dot{\sigma}_{kl}(t'). \quad (1.7)$$

The time reversed process $\bar{\sigma}_{kl}(t)$ delivers the same amount of work to the material as the original one. Hence it can be assumed, that the energy differences ΔW are the same in both processes, i.e.

$$\Delta W\{\bar{\sigma}_{kl}(\cdot)\} = \Delta W\{\sigma_{kl}(\cdot)\}. \quad (1.8)$$

This statement is called macroscopic reversibility.¹⁾ Insertion of eqs. (1.5) and (1.7) thus yields

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt \dot{\sigma}_{ij}(t) \int_{-\infty}^t dt' L_{ijkl}(t-t') \dot{\sigma}_{kl}(t') = 0, \quad (1.9)$$

where the abbreviation

$$L_{ijkl}(t) \equiv I_{ijkl}(t) - I_{klij}(t) = -L_{klij}(t), \quad t \geq 0 \quad (1.10)$$

has been introduced. From eq. (1.9) general conclusions on $L_{ijkl}(t)$ can be obtained. To derive them we insert the piecewise linear closed stress history of figure 1, use the antisymmetry of L_{ijkl} , its independence of the stress history and obtain by the mean value theorem in integral calculus in the limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$

$$L_{ijkl}(t_1) - L_{ijkl}(t_2) + L_{ijkl}(t_2 - t_1) = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

for all t_1, t_2 in $0 < t_1 < t_2$. (For the proof compare (6)). The only continuous solution of eq. (1.11) is $L_{ijkl}(t) = t L_{ijkl}(1)$ for $t \geq 0$. For the materials with reversible stress-strain behavior however, $L_{ijkl}(t)$ must be finite for all $t \geq 0$. This requires $L_{ijkl}(1) = 0$ and hence

$$L_{ijkl}(t) \equiv 0, \quad t \geq 0. \quad (1.12)$$

By eqs. (1.10) and (1.3) we have thus proven, under the assumption of an energy density which is invariant against time reversal, that the after-effect tensors are totally symmetric i.e.

$$I_{ijkl}(t) = I_{jikl}(t) = I_{ijlk}(t) = I_{klij}(t), \quad t \geq 0. \quad (1.13)$$

This result holds generally for anisotropic materials. The after-effect tensors contain therefore at most 21 independent components.

¹⁾ MEIXNER (5) has shown, that the statements of macroscopic and microscopic reversibility are the same for linear systems. Moreover, they are equivalent with ONSAGER symmetries for the linear system eq. (1.1).

2. Material Symmetry

The given constitutive equations can be simplified, if the material possesses any symmetry in its undeformed (homogeneous) reference state. Allowable symmetry transformations of a solid are those rotations and inflections which carry the body into indistinguishable positions. They can be represented by coordinate transformations of the coordinates in the undeformed state

$$\bar{x}_i = \frac{\partial \bar{x}_i}{\partial x_j} x_j = S_{ij} x_j, \quad (2.1)$$

where S_{ij} are orthogonal matrices with $S_{ij} S_{ik} = \delta_{jk}$, $S_{ij} S_{kj} = \delta_{ik}$, $\det \|S_{ij}\| = \pm 1$.

The physical properties of the materials are not changed by symmetry transformations. Hence the stress-strain relation eq. (1.1) must be form-invariant against the transformations eq. (2.1), i.e. besides eq. (1.1) also

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \bar{I}_{ijkl}(t-t') d\bar{\sigma}_{kl}(t') \quad (2.2)$$

must hold. Since both the deformation tensor and the stress tensor refer to the coordinates of the undeformed state in the linear theory, they transform as

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}(t) = S_{ik} S_{jl} \epsilon_{kl}(t), \quad \bar{\sigma}_{ij}(t) = S_{ik} S_{jl} \sigma_{kl}(t). \quad (2.3)$$

Insertion of eqs. (2.3) in eq. (2.2) and comparison with eq. (1.1) thus yields

$$\bar{I}_{ijkl}(t) = S_{im} S_{jn} S_{ko} S_{lp} I_{mnop}(t). \quad (2.4)$$

Due to the form-invariance, the functions $\bar{I}_{ijkl}(t)$ must be the same as the functions $I_{ijkl}(t)$. Thus they are independent of the elements of the transformation matrices S_{ij} . Hence eq. (2.4) is the basis for the reduction of $I_{ijkl}(t)$ for known symmetry transformations S_{ij} .

In connection with the fiber reinforced plastics we consider only two symmetry classes.

a. Transversely isotropic material

We consider an isotropic matrix material which is reinforced by fibers in x_3 -direction. The fibers may intersect the x_1, x_2 -plane randomly. Such a reinforced material is isotropic with respect to arbitrary rotations around the x_3 -axis and allows inflections at the x_1, x_2 -plane. The symmetry transformations are therefore

$$1. \quad \bar{x}_1 = x_1, \quad \bar{x}_2 = x_2, \quad \bar{x}_3 = -x_3; \quad (2.5)$$

$$2. \quad \bar{x}_1 = x_1 \cos \varphi + x_2 \sin \varphi, \quad \bar{x}_2 = -x_1 \sin \varphi + x_2 \cos \varphi, \quad \bar{x}_3 = x_3$$

The corresponding transformation matrices $S_{ij} = \partial \bar{x}_i / \partial x_j$ are easily obtained and insertion into eq. (2.4) yields after a lengthy calculation on account of eq. (1.13)

$$\begin{aligned} I_{1111}(t) &= I_{2222}(t) = I_{1122}(t) + 2I_{1212}(t), \quad I_{3333}(t) \neq 0; \\ I_{1133}(t) &= I_{2233}(t), \quad I_{1313}(t) = I_{2323}(t), \\ I_{1112}(t) &= I_{1222}(t) = I_{1233}(t) = I_{1323}(t) = 0; \\ I_{3jk1}(t) &= 0 \quad (j, k, l \neq 3); \quad I_{3331}(t) = 0 \quad (l \neq 3). \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Hence the after-effect tensor of the transversely isotropic material consists of 5 independent components which in analogy to linear elasticity may be written:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{1111}(t - \tau_0) &\equiv \frac{1}{E_{11}(t)} = I_{2222}(t - \tau_0) \equiv \frac{1}{E_{22}(t)}, \quad I_{3333}(t - \tau_0) \equiv \frac{1}{E_{33}(t)}; \\ I_{1122}(t - \tau_0) &\equiv \frac{-v_{12}(t)}{E_{11}(t)} = \frac{-v_{21}(t)}{E_{22}(t)}, \\ I_{1133}(t - \tau_0) &\equiv \frac{-v_{13}(t)}{E_{11}(t)} = \frac{-v_{31}(t)}{E_{33}(t)} = I_{2233}(t - \tau_0) \equiv \frac{-v_{23}(t)}{E_{22}(t)} = \frac{-v_{32}(t)}{E_{33}(t)}; \quad (2.7) \\ I_{1212}(t - \tau_0) &\equiv \frac{1}{4G_{12}(t)} = \frac{1 + v_{12}(t)}{2E_{11}(t)}, \\ I_{1313}(t - \tau_0) &\equiv \frac{1}{4G_{13}(t)} = I_{2323}(t - \tau_0) \equiv \frac{1}{4G_{23}(t)}. \end{aligned}$$

The notations are chosen such that for a single stress jump at $t = \tau_0$ $E(t)$, $v(t)$ and $G(t)$ have the meaning of time dependent YOUNG'S moduli, POISSON'S ratios and shear moduli, respectively.

b. Orthotropic material (reinforcement ratio $\neq 1$)

Next we consider an isotropic matrix material, which is reinforced in the x_1 - and x_2 directions by fibers of different strengths. These fibers may form an orthogonal plane network. The compound material may be built up of parallel equidistant layers of those networks. Such a material allows independent 180° -rotations around the x_1 -, x_2 - and x_3 -axes, respectively, as symmetry transformations

$$\begin{aligned} 1. \quad \bar{x}_1 &= x_1, \quad \bar{x}_2 = -x_2, \quad \bar{x}_3 = -x_3; \\ 2. \quad \bar{x}_1 &= -x_1, \quad \bar{x}_2 = x_2, \quad \bar{x}_3 = -x_3; \\ 3. \quad \bar{x}_1 &= -x_1, \quad \bar{x}_2 = -x_2, \quad \bar{x}_3 = x_3. \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

As before we conclude from eqs. (2.4) and (1.13)

$$I_{1111}(t) = 0 \quad (l \neq 1), \quad I_{1jk1}(t) = 0 \quad (j, k, l \neq 1); \quad (2.9)$$

$$I_{1123}(t) = I_{1213}(t) = I_{2223}(t) = I_{2333}(t) = 0, \quad (2.9)$$

and there remain 9 independent components of I_{ijkl} for the orthotropic material:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{1111}(t-\tau_0) &\equiv \frac{1}{E_{11}(t)}, & I_{2222}(t-\tau_0) &\equiv \frac{1}{E_{22}(t)}, & I_{3333}(t-\tau_0) &\equiv \frac{1}{E_{33}(t)} \\ I_{1122}(t-\tau_0) &\equiv -\frac{\nu_{12}(t)}{E_{11}(t)} = -\frac{\nu_{21}(t)}{E_{22}(t)}, \\ I_{1133}(t-\tau_0) &\equiv -\frac{\nu_{13}(t)}{E_{11}(t)} = -\frac{\nu_{31}(t)}{E_{33}(t)}, \\ I_{2233}(t-\tau_0) &\equiv -\frac{\nu_{23}(t)}{E_{22}(t)} = -\frac{\nu_{32}(t)}{E_{33}(t)}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

$$I_{1212}(t-\tau_0) \equiv \frac{1}{4G_{12}(t)}, \quad I_{1313}(t-\tau_0) \equiv \frac{1}{4G_{13}(t)}, \quad I_{2323}(t-\tau_0) \equiv \frac{1}{4G_{23}(t)}.$$

B. Experiments

3. General Remarks

The comparison of the theoretical with the experimental results requires the tensorial eq. (1.1) to be written in components. It is convenient to introduce the following abbreviations:

$$\sigma_{11} \equiv \sigma_1, \quad \sigma_{22} \equiv \sigma_2, \quad \sigma_{33} \equiv \sigma_3; \quad (3.1)$$

$$\epsilon_{11} \equiv \epsilon_1, \quad \epsilon_{22} \equiv \epsilon_2, \quad \epsilon_{33} \equiv \epsilon_3; \quad \epsilon_{ik} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{ik} \quad (i \neq k).$$

All experiments have been made at thin plates. At loading in the reinforcement (x_1, x_2) plane approximately plane states of stress result for which $\sigma_3 = \sigma_{13} = \sigma_{23} = 0$. Neglecting ϵ_3 , we thus obtain from eqs. (1.1), (1.13); (2.6) and (2.7) or (2.9) and (2.10), respectively, the following relations

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1(t) &= \int_{-\infty}^t \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}(t-t'+\tau_0)} d\sigma_1(t') - \frac{\nu_{21}(t-t'+\tau_0)}{E_{22}(t-t'+\tau_0)} d\sigma_2(t') \right], \\ \epsilon_2(t) &= \int_{-\infty}^t \left[-\frac{\nu_{12}(t-t'+\tau_0)}{E_{11}(t-t'+\tau_0)} d\sigma_1(t') + \frac{1}{E_{22}(t-t'+\tau_0)} d\sigma_2(t') \right], \\ \gamma_{12}(t) &= \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{1}{G_{12}(t-t'+\tau_0)} d\sigma_{12}(t'). \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

The constitutive functions E_{11} , E_{22} etc. satisfy different symmetry relations. These are for the

a. orthotropic material (reinforcement ratio $\neq 1$)

$$E_{11}(t) \neq E_{22}(t), \quad \frac{\nu_{12}(t)}{E_{11}(t)} = \frac{\nu_{21}(t)}{E_{22}(t)}, \quad (3.3)$$

$G_{12}(t)$ = independent constitutive function ;

b. transversely isotropic material

$$E_{11}(t) = E_{12}(t), \quad \nu_{12}(t) = \nu_{21}(t), \quad G_{12}(t) = \frac{E_{11}(t)}{2(1+\nu_{12}(t))}. \quad (3.4)$$

The experiments have been performed with glassfiber reinforced completely tempered unsaturated polyester resins (UP-resin). The experimental program has been designed with special emphasis to check the linearity and reversibility of the stress-strain behavior as well as the symmetry relations and the superposition principle.

4. Creep under Constant Uniaxial Load resp. Pure Shear

For the special stress history as shown in figure 2.1. follows from eqs. (3.2):

$$\epsilon_{1,2}(t) = \frac{\sigma_{1,2}}{E_{11,22}(t)}, \quad \gamma_{12}(t) = \frac{\sigma_{12}}{G_{12}(t)}. \quad (4.1)$$

The relations are experimentally verified for orthotropic glass-fiber fabric (7,8,9) as well as transversely isotropic glassfiber mat (7,8,10,11) reinforced UP-resins. To verify eqs. (4.1) isochronous stress-strain diagrams (fig. 2.3) are constructed from measurements of time dependent deformations (fig. 2.2). For the materials under consideration there exist linear domains which are limited by a material damage in the form of microcracking, (12). Under uniaxial constant tension resp. compression the magnitudes of the time dependent strain in the load direction are nearly the same, (7,12).

4.1 Moduli

The creeping moduli (constitutive functions) are experimentally determined according to figure 2. The following relations are obtained for times in $0 < \tau_0 < \tau^* \leq t$:

$$E_{11,22}(t) = E_{11,22}(\tau_0) \left(\frac{t}{\tau_0} \right)^{-k_{1,2}} = E_{11,22}(\tau_0^*) \left(\frac{t}{\tau_0} \right)^{-k_{1,2}}, \quad (4.2)$$

$$G_{12}(t) = G_{12}(\tau_0) \left(\frac{t}{\tau_0} \right)^{-k_{12}} = G_{12}(\tau_0^*) \left(\frac{t}{\tau_0} \right)^{-k_{12}}, \quad (4.3)$$

where $0 < k_{1,2} < 0.5$ and $0 < k_{12} < 0.5$ in the temperature range $0 \leq \vartheta \leq 80^\circ\text{C}$, and at glass contents between $0 \leq \varphi \leq 60$ vol.-%. $\tau_0 > 0$ is the moment at which the constant load is supplied. The spontaneous deformations $\epsilon_{1,2}(\tau_0)$ resp. $\gamma_{12}(\tau_0)$ and hence the spontaneous moduli $E_{11,22}(\tau_0)$ and $G_{12}(\tau_0)$ cannot be measured very

accurately. Only at a later time t_0^* the deformations can be measured accurately; the spontaneous values are obtained by extrapolation (cp. fig. 2.2. and 2.4).

The constitutive functions eqs. (4.2) and (4.3) are experimentally determined for times in $t^* = 10^{-1} \text{ h} \leq t \leq 2 \cdot 10 \text{ h}$. $E_{11,22}(t^*)$ and $G_{12}(t^*)$ resp. $k_{1,2}$ and k_{12} depend on the temperature and the glass content, cp. (12). For the transversely isotropic UP-resins the relations $E_{11}(t^*) = E_{22}(t^*)$ and $k_1 = k_2$ are measured for temperatures between $0^\circ \leq t \leq 80^\circ \text{ C}$ and glass contents between $0 \leq \varphi \leq 33 \text{ Vol. - \%}$ to within a relative standard error of $\pm 9 \%$, (12). The same standard error is expected for the orthotropic materials.

4.2 POISSON'S ratio

The POISSON'S ratios ν_{12} and ν_{21} for the orthotropic glass-fiber reinforced UP-resins at constant uniaxial load are different functions of time, cp. fig. 3.

For the transversely isotropic glassfiber mat reinforced UP-resins follow from deformation measurements at constant uniaxial tension resp. compression, that the ratios $\nu_{12} = \nu_{21}$ and ν_{13} are constant in time, cp. fig. 4. As can be seen from fig. 4³ too, a constant increase of the deformation rate up to $\epsilon_1 = 1.2 \%$ has no influence on ν_{12} and ν_{13} .

4.3 Symmetry relations

The symmetry relation eq. (3.3)₂ for an orthotropic glass-fiber fabric reinforced UP-resin is confirmed in fig. 5. Since $E_{11} = E_{22}$ for a reinforcement ratio of 1 : 1, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{21}$ is confirmed too.

For the transversely isotropic glassfiber reinforced UP-resins a comparison of the measured and with eq. (3.4.)₃ calculated shear moduli are in good agreement, c.p. fig. 6. The calculations have been made with the values $E_{11}(t) = E_{22}(t)$ of fig. 6 and with the constant POISSON'S ratio $\nu_{12} = \nu_{21}$ of fig. 4; for the exponents holds $k_1 = k_2 = k_{12}$.

4.4. On the reversibility of the stress-strain behavior

Under the action of external forces in the reinforcement plane of glassfiber reinforced UP-resins adhesive (resin) resp. cohesive (interface glass resin) bonds may break in micro-regions of the compound material. This bond breaking occurs at certain critical deformations. It causes a locally limited irreversible loosening along those fibers, which are (nearly) perpendicular to the maximum tension. An opening of imperfections at the interface glassresin may join the bond breaking. This effect is called micro-cracking; failure due to fracture occurs at higher loadings.

The critical extension at micro-cracking is independent of the glass content, the deformation velocity, the time, the kind of loading (static, step-wise, vibrating), the kind of the stress

distribution (uni- or biaxial) and it is independent of the temperature in a wide range; however, it is specific for every material, c.p. (13).

Micro-cracking has an effect on the birefringence of translucent materials, therefore it is easily observed by the un-weaponed eye. In not translucent materials it is observed by an electron microscope. There is some uncertainty to adjoin a definit value of critical extension to the first appearance of micro-cracks. Therefore a constant deformation interval is associated with micro-cracking.

The stress-strain behavior for glassfiber reinforced UP-resins is reversible as long as the deformation in the direction of the maximum tension stays below this constant critical deformation interval, c.p. fig. 7. Up to this deformation interval the stress-strain behavior is linear, (14).

5. Comparison of Measured and Calculated Deformations

In order to check the superposition principle some relatively complicated stress histories may be discussed.

5.1 Step-shaped uniaxial stress history

For the stress history as shown in fig. 8 eq. (3.2)₁ simplifies for all t in $\tau_n > t \geq \tau_{n-1} + (\tau_o^* - \tau_o)$ and all $n = 1, 2, \dots$:

$$\epsilon_1(t) = \frac{\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_o)}{E_{11}(t-\tau_o+\tau_o)} + \frac{\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_1)}{E_{11}(t-\tau_1+\tau_o)} + \dots + \frac{\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_{n-1})}{E_{11}(t-\tau_{n-1}+\tau_o)} \quad (5.1)$$

$\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_k) \equiv \sigma_1(\tau_k+0) - \sigma_1(\tau_k-0)$ denotes the stress jump at τ_k . The instant t must be chosen such, that at t no jump is present and that the time argument in E_{11} of the last term in the sum is larger or equal to a time τ_o^* , for which E_{11} first can be measured. As can be seen in fig. 8 the measured and by eq. (5.1) calculated values of $\epsilon_1(t)$ are in good agreement.

5.2 Step-shaped biaxial stress history

For the biaxial stress history as shown in fig. 9 follow from eqs. (3.2) and (3.4) for the transversely isotropic material

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_1(t) = & \frac{1}{E_{11}(t)} \left[\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_o) - \nu_{12}(t)\Delta\sigma_2(\tau_o) \right] + \\ & + \frac{\theta(t-\tau_1)}{E_{11}(t-\tau_1+\tau_o)} \left[\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_1) - \nu_{12}(t-\tau_1+\tau_o)\Delta\sigma_2(\tau_1) \right], \quad (5.2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\epsilon_2(t) = \frac{1}{E_{11}(t)} \left[-\nu_{12}(t)\Delta\sigma_1(\tau_o) + \Delta\sigma_2(\tau_o) \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{\Theta(t - \tau_1)}{E_{11}(t - \tau_1 + \tau_0)} \left[-v_{12}(t - \tau_1 + \tau_0) \Delta \sigma_1(\tau_1) + \Delta \sigma_2(\tau_1) \right] \quad (5.2)$$

for all $t > \tau_1$. $\Theta(t - \tau_1)$ denotes the HEAVISIDE unit step. The agreement of the measured and with eqs. (5.2) calculated values of $\epsilon_1(t)$ and $\epsilon_2(t)$ is good, even in the domain of irreversible stress-strain behavior, as can be seen in fig. 9.

5.3. Uniaxial sinusoidal vibrating stress history

For an uniaxial stress history consisting of a constant mean stress $\sigma_1^{(m)}$ and a sinusoidal vibrating stress with constant amplitude $\sigma_1^{(a)}$ (cp. fig. 10) we obtain from eqs. (3.2)₁ and (4.2)

$$\epsilon_1(t) = \frac{1}{E_{11}(t)} \left[\sigma_1^{(m)} + F_{11}(t; \omega, k_1) \sigma_1^{(a)} \right], \quad (5.3)$$

where

$$F_{11}(t; \omega, k_1) \equiv \omega t \int_{\tau_0/t}^1 x^{k_1} \cos[\omega t(1-x)] dx. \quad (5.4)$$

Some remarks on internal heat dissipation must be made: The glassfiber mat reinforced UP-resins have high YOUNG's moduli but relatively small damping. This leads in the temperature range $-20^\circ\text{C} \leq \vartheta \leq 60^\circ\text{C}$, for glass contents between $13.5 \leq \Psi \leq 20$ Vol.-%, at mean stresses in $0 \leq \sigma_1^{(m)} \leq 600$ kp/cm², for frequencies $f = \omega/2\pi \leq 10$ hz (r.p.s) and stress amplitudes between $0 < \sigma_1^{(a)} \leq 250$ kp/cm² to a stationary thermal equilibrium due to heat exchange with the surroundings. The heat dissipation increases the surface temperatures to maximal $\Delta\vartheta = 7^\circ\text{C}$ compared to the temperature of the surroundings. Temperature gradients inside the sample can be neglected, c.p. [15]. Hence, after a short period of internal heating, a constant temperature is reached. For the experiments which are shown in fig. 10 the maximal temperature difference was smaller than 1°C .

The integral F_{11} of eq. (5.4) has been calculated on a computer for a given temperature and frequency, the result is shown in fig. 10. This leads to a very small contribution $\epsilon_1^{(a)}(t)$ in the total deformation, which is nearly constant in time. Thus, with sufficient accuracy the creeping behavior can be described alone by $\epsilon_1^{(m)}(t) = \sigma_1^{(m)}/E_{11}(t)$, as is shown in fig. 10 by the good agreement of the measured and calculated values. A more detailed discussion can be found in [16].

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Fig. 1: Piecewise linear closed stress history with fixed times $t_1 > 0$, $t_2 > 0$, arbitrary δ in $0 < \delta < \min(t_1, t_2)$ and arbitrary constant symmetric tensors A_{kl} and B_{kl} .

Table I: Unsaturated Polyester-resins used

symbol	type	producer
UP 1	Leguval N 30	Bayer AG, Leverkusen
UP 5	Vestopal 150	Chemische Werke Hüls AG, Marl

Table II: Manufacturing of Laminates

compound materials	hardener/weight-portion [%] accelerator/weight-portion [%]	manufacturing under air closure; temperature [°C]	hardening in air; temperature [°C]/time [h]
GSM1-UP1 GSG1-UP1(2:1) GSG2-UP1(1:1)	50 percent methyl-ethyl-ketonperoxide/2 Co-accelerator/0,2 (1 percent cobaltoctoat-solution)	handlaminated 23	100/24
GSM1-UP5	benzoylperoxide paste/2 10 percent diethylanilin/0,3	handlaminated 23	100/24

GSM: transversely-isotropic, GSG: orthotropic

--- extrapolation of experimental results

Fig. 2: Schematic outline for the determination of the moduli at constant uniaxial stress $\sigma_{1,2}$ resp. pure shear stress σ_{12} ($\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = 0$); isothermal process.

Fig. 3: POISSON'S ratios of orthotropic compound materials at different reinforcement ratios, ; constant uniaxial tension; mean values each of 5 single curves; (7,12).

Fig. 4: POISSON'S ratios in dependence on time and deformation in loading direction; konstant uniaxial tension resp. compression with following deformation increase; mean values each of 7 single curves; (7,12).

Fig. 5: Ratios of POISSON's numbers ν_{12}/ν_{21} and YOUNG's moduli E_{11}/E_{22} as functions of time, mean values each of 5 single curves; (7, 12).

Fig. 6: Measured and with eq. (3.4)₃ calculated shear moduli G_{12} as function of time; $G_{12}(t)$: single measurements, $E_{11}(t)$: mean values each of 5 single curves; (7,12).

Fig. 7: Reversible and irreversible stress-strain behavior at relieve of load after preceding constant uniaxial tension; mean values each of 5 single curves; (12).

Fig. 8: Calculated and measured deformations as functions of time; step-shaped uniaxial tension; single experimental results; (12).

Fig. 9: Calculated and measured deformations as functions of time; thin-walled pipe under step wise changing internal pressure, single experiments.

